

Report from GHRSSST RDAC

AUSTRALIAN GOVERNMENT BUREAU OF METEOROLOGY

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Australian RDAC – Progress since June 2019

Helen Beggs, Pallavi Govekar, Lixin Qi, Chris Griffin

<http://imos.org.au/sstproducts.html>

GHR SST GDS2 L4 Products

- RAMSSA and GAMSSA SST analyses now available in GDS2.0 format from PO.DAAC back to 2006
- ACSPO NOAA-20 and Suomi-NPP VIIRS L3U SST ingested into RAMSSA (from 17 Nov 2019) and GAMSSA (from 29 Apr 2020)
 - See Helen Beggs' G-XXI Tue Session 3 Presentation

GHR SST GDS2 L3C/L3S Products

- OSI-SAF MetOp-B AVHRR L2P and ACSPO NOAA-20 VIIRS L3U SSTs added to operational IMOS 0.02° Multi-sensor L3S and L3C (from 21 Nov 2019)
- Reprocessed IMOS AVHRR + VIIRS L3C/L3S fv02 products from 2017 to 2018 (total archive now 1992-2018)
- Experimented with adding Sentinel-3A/B SLSTR L2P SSTs to Multi-sensor L3S
 - See Pallavi Govekar's G-XXI Wed Session 4 Presentation

1-day 9 km RAMSSA L4 SSTfnd

1-day 25 km GAMSSA L4 SSTfnd

N18, MB, NPP, N20

1-day night 2 km Multi-sensor L3S SSTskin

1-day night 2 km NOAA-20 L3C SSTskin

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ISAR SSTskin from RV Investigator

Helen Beggs, Janice Sisson, Nicole Morgan

<http://imos.org.au/sstsensors.html>

- **1 Oct 2014:** Infrared Autonomous SST Radiometer installed on RV Investigator along with SBE38 water intake temperature sensor
- **24 Mar 2016 onwards:** Real-time ISAR SSTskin and SBE38 SSTdepth available from AODN:
http://thredds.aodn.org.au/thredds/catalog/IMOS/SOOP/SOOP-ASF/VLMJ_Investigator/meteorological_sst_observations/catalog.html
- **Oct 2014 – Mar 2019:** Reprocessed ISAR data in L2R format available from <http://www.marlin.csiro.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/search#!bdf91f86-2968-4711-873e-2761383bb207> and <http://www.ships4sst.org>, and in IMOS format from AODN
 - Used to study cool-skin effect (Zhang et al., 2020, *JTECH*, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-19-0161.1>) and to validate JAXA Himawari-8 SST (Yang et al., 2020, *Remote Sensing*, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12081237>)

- **Apr 2019 - Mar 2020** ISAR data currently being reprocessed
- Excellent examples of diurnal warming north of Australia during 19 Oct – 17 Dec 2019 Maritime Continent Cruise IN2019_V06. Shown here are plots for 15 – 18 Nov 2019.

